

The Reduction of Unsymmetrical Dichloracetone by Yeast.

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The reduction of chlorinated ketones does not appear to have been studied hitherto, although the reduction of aldehydes and ketones in general by yeast has been the subject of thorough investigation by Neuberg¹ and his co-workers. Their work conclusively proves the value of yeast as a reducing agent, which must play an important part in ordinary fermentation as also in natural syntheses. The first important example of bio-chemical reduction of this nature was furnished by Linter,² Liebig, and Lüers who reduced chloral hydrate and made the preparation of trichlorethyl alcohol accessible in the laboratory. The importance of reducing monochloracetone, or indeed, of any of the unsymmetrical chloracetones by means of yeast, lies firstly in the fact that these acetones after reduction give rise to alcohols containing an asymmetric carbon atom as is evident from the following :

Secondly, these chlorinated secondary alcohols would form the basis of urethane derivatives, valuable as soporifics. In ordinary chemical reduction it is the

¹ C. Neuberg and J. Kerb. Ber. 46, 2225 (1913).

² C. J. Linter and H. J. V. Liebig H. 72, 449 (1911); Linter and Lüers. H. 85, 122 (1913).

racemic form that is invariably obtained, as the chance of formation of the dextro-form is equal to the chance of formation of the laevo-form. In the case of biochemical reduction, the chance of obtaining optically active components is usually great due to the selective action of enzymes, and if in any way the preponderance of one isomer over the other can be secured, the resulting compound should exhibit optical activity (compare Neuberg and Kerb; Neuberg and Nord). An early example of the selective action of ferments or bacteria is to be found in Le Bel's work on the fermentation of inactive propylene glycol by *bacterium termo*. A further example of interest is to be found in the work of Peré,¹ who studied the biochemical oxidation of propylene glycol in contact with *tyrothrix tenuis*. It is significant that this investigator obtained a dextro-rotating propyl glycol, as distinct from the laevo rotatory propyl glycol obtained by Le Bel. The explanation must evidently lie in the use of different bacteria, which would seem to indicate with a degree of certainty that the action of the two bacteria upon racemic propyl glycol is selective.

The particular reaction described in these pages is a case of reduction by yeast in a fermenting solution of sugar. Here also the yeast exerts a selective action and from unsymmetrical dichloracetone gives rise to an optically active dichlorisopropyl alcohol. The rate of this reduction, however, in the case of dichloracetone is relatively rapid as the reduction is probably completed in 24 hours if not in 12 hours. The operation of adding a 20 per cent. alcoholic solution of 10 grams dichloracetone to a fermenting solution of sugar requires 3-4 hours, after which the mixture is allowed to stand

¹ Annales de l'Institut Pasteur, 1896, 11, 600-2.

overnight in an incubator at 35°C. Next morning the odour of dichloracetone is scarcely to be noticed in the reaction mixture, and the sugar is also found to have disappeared to the extent of 96-97 per cent. The further addition of yeast, or of yeast and sugar, is only to secure certainty of reduction of any dichloracetone that might have remained unacted upon. Dichloracetone does not seem to be appreciably poisonous to beer-yeast and the yield of dichlorisopropyl alcohol is not affected by the rate of addition of the dichloracetone to the fermenting sugar solution. In one experiment in which accidentally the stopper of the dropping funnel was dislodged, about half of the alcoholic solution of dichloracetone fell at once into the fermenting sugar solution without markedly affecting the rate of fermentation of the solution. This non-poisonous character of dichloracetone is convenient and also interesting in view of the fact that Willstätter has recently found bromal very poisonous to yeast and Neuberg (*loc. cit.*) found it necessary to add the aldehydes with which he experimented, very cautiously to the fermenting solution in order to get a good yield of reduction product. Also in some experiments with monochloracetone the rate of addition was found to be very important. The first experiment was conducted with monochloracetone supplied by Messrs. Kahlbaum of Berlin, an alcoholic solution of which had to be very cautiously added in order to maintain the fermentation of the sugar solution. In fact even with the utmost care, it was difficult to maintain a brisk fermentation throughout the addition, and towards the end the addition of monochloracetone had actually to be suspended, in view of the considerably decreased rate of fermentation. It is to be observed here that in course of further investigation, it was found that the monochloracetone supplied by Messrs.

Kahlbaum was not pure, but contained a considerably higher percentage of chlorine than is required by the formula. This may be due either to the presence of some dichloroacetone, the boiling point of which closely approaches that of monochloroacetone, or to small quantities of higher chlorinated products. The conclusion, therefore, is that either monochloroacetone or the very small quantities of tri-, tetra-, or penta-, chlor derivative of acetone, are poisonous towards yeast, dichloroacetone itself having scarcely any injurious effect. Experiments with monochloroacetone alone could not be completed on account of the difficulty in obtaining a pure specimen of the substance. Its preparation has now been undertaken. In the case of monochloroacetone something different occurs, as the peculiar penetrating odour of this compound remains for over a week, and indeed does not then entirely disappear. In our experiments we followed the conversion of monochloroacetone into monochloroisopropyl alcohol by the disappearance of this unpleasant and tear-bringing odour. As already mentioned, the poisonous nature of monochloroacetone or any component with which it is contaminated, is so marked that a little carelessness in the addition of its alcoholic solution to the fermenting sugar solution speedily stops the fermentation. It is significant that monochloroacetone has a fatal action upon yeast, whereas dichloroacetone has practically no such injurious action. A careful comparison of the various chloroacetones with regard to their action on yeast would be of interest and it is hoped that a future communication may be made thereon.

Whilst in the cases cited above (Neuberg, Pere, Le Bel) the rotation in two experiments was not constant, with dichloroacetone however, this has been found to be the same in five separate experiments that have up to now been performed.

An additional interest in obtaining unsymmetrical dichlorisopropyl alcohol by the biochemical method lies in the ease with which a good and cheap yield of this alcohol can be obtained, rendering the process thereby suitable for practical application.

Several experiments have up till now been performed both with the alcohol itself and its urethane derivative, upon rabbits, which justify the expectation that they will be valuable as soporifics. It is to be observed that dichlorisopropyl alcohol is likely to have an advantage over chloral, being poorer in chlorine, and more effective than trichlor ethyl alcohol, being a secondary alcohol. All experiments, that as yet it has been possible to conduct, show that both the alcohol and the urethane derivative are without any injurious effect upon the animal system, and that the difference between the narcotic and toxic doses is fairly considerable. A more detailed report of the investigation in this direction will be shortly communicated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

250 grams of starch sugar or ordinary cane sugar were dissolved in 2.5 litres of tap water at 40° in a 5 litre bottle. To the solution 250 grams of pressed beer-yeast were added. In about fifteen minutes the liquid was in brisk fermentation, when a 25 per cent. alcoholic solution of 10 grams dichloracetone was drop by drop added to the fermenting mixture, care being taken not to suppress the vigorous fermentation by too quick addition of the dichloracetone solution. In three to four hours the addition is complete, during which time the bottle is shaken from time to time. The reaction vessel is then allowed to stand over-night in an incubator at 35°C. Next morning the odour of dichloracetone

is found to have practically disappeared, and the sugar also almost fully used up. In order to ensure more complete reduction, about 100 grams more yeast are added and left again in the incubator for two more days, at the end of which the liquid is filtered, the residue washed two or three times and the combined filtrate distilled under vacuum on a boiling water-bath. The ethyl alcohol, dichlorisopropyl alcohol and any unchanged dichloracetone being volatile in steam, collect in the receiver which is constantly kept well-cooled by a rapid current of tap water. The distillate is now shaken up with two litres of ether, the ethereal layer separated, dried over ignited sodium sulphate, and distilled off from a water bath. The residue which now amounts to 8 cc. is fractionated from a small distilling flask, when 5.2 grams of dichlorisopropyl alcohol collect steadily at 146° - 148° [compare Wohl and Roth, Ber. 40, 217 (1907)]. The fore-fraction also contains about a gram of the dichlorisopropyl alcohol identified by its optical rotation. From a large scale experiment with 48 grams of dichloracetone, 26 grams of the pure alcohol were obtained, which correspond to a yield of 54 per cent. of the theory.

Dichlorisopropyl alcohol is moderately soluble in water and very soluble in ether and alcohol. It has a burning sweet taste, and a pleasant ethereal odour, having a density of 1.33. The pure liquid in a one decimeter tube rotates the plane of polarisation by -11.88° . $[\alpha]_D$ is therefore -9° .

Found C=27.83, H=4.76, Cl=54.0; $C_3H_5OCl_2$, requires

C=27.91, H=4.65, Cl=55.0 per cent.

The urethane derivative $\text{CHCl}_2 \cdot \overset{\text{CH}_3}{\underset{|}{\text{CH}}} \cdot \text{O} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH}_2$ is prepared by mixing an ethereal solution of carbamyl chloride

with the calculated quantity of dichlorisopropyl alcohol also in ethereal solution. The solution is allowed to stand at room temperature for 15 minutes, after which the ether is expelled on the water-bath. The residual oil soon solidifies on scratching with a glass rod and can then be crystallised either from ether in which it is extremely soluble, or from water in which it is soluble only to the extent of 2 per cent. at ordinary temperature. This is a decided advantage as the loss in crystallising from ether is excessive. The urethane crystallises in white needles, melting at 61° - 63° C.

0.1330 gave $N=9.4$ cc., at 16° C and 755 mm. press ; $N=8.20$; $C_4H_7O_2NCl_2$ requires $N=8.14$ per cent. 0.75 gram of the urethane dissolved in 25 cc. of water and 2 cc. of glycerine when given to a rabbit weighing 4.5 pounds caused an uninterrupted sleep for 11 hours. The parent alcohol given in 0.5 gram caused an undisturbed sleep in the same animal for a period of one hour, without spasms. The urethane derivative is also optically active, rotating the plane of polarisation to the left. 0.3336 gram dissolved in 2 cc. of absolute alcohol, rotated the plane through -2.226° in a 1 dm. tube. The reduction of monochloracetone (from Kahlbaum) by a method similar to that adopted in the case of dichloracetone, resulted in a yield of not more than 25 per cent. In fractionating the final product of reduction after extraction with ether, the first part of the distillate, after expulsion of the ether distilled under 100° C and contained mostly ethyl alcohol ; the fraction distilling between 100° and 125° contained unconverted monochloracetone and also a small quantity of monochlorisopropyl alcohol, CH_2Cl . $CH(OH)$. CH_3 , the boiling point of which latter is 127° . Then came a fraction boiling between 126° and 132° which may be taken as more or less pure monochlorisopropyl alcohol, but the thermometer then rose rapidly, a product boiling

between 138° and 152° was collected which probably marks the boiling point limits of a mixture of mono- and dichlorisopropyl alcohol. After this the thermometer rose steadily up to 180° and a few drops of liquid of unknown composition were obtained.

Fig. 1